

Academic General Practice
C110 Health Sciences Centre
Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland

T +353 1 716 6696
F +353 1 716 6549

Cleachtas Ginearálta Acadúil,
C110, An Coláiste Ollscoile, Baile Átha
Cliath,
Belfield, Baile Átha Cliath 4, Eire

www.ucd.ie/medicine
postgraduate.medicine@ucd.ie

Consent Form – Staff

<i>I have read and understood the Information Leaflet about this research project. The information has been fully explained to me and I have been able to ask questions, all of which have been answered to my satisfaction.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>I understand that I don't have to take part in this study and that I can opt out at any time. I understand that I don't have to give a reason for opting out.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>I am aware of the potential risks of this research study.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>I have been given a copy of the Information Leaflet and this completed consent form for my records.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Storage and future use of information: <i>I give my permission for information I provide, to be stored or electronically processed. By doing so I consent to this information being used in <u>related or other studies in the future</u>. Further, I understand that studies of this nature will need to receive their own ethical approvals and that my data will also be anonymous in these studies.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>I agree to take part in the above research study.</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

Participant Name (Block Capitals): _____

Participant Signature: _____

Phone: _____

Date: _____

To be completed by the Principal Investigator or nominee.

I the undersigned, have taken the time to fully explain to the above participant the nature and purpose of this study in a manner that they could understand. I have explained the risks involved as well as the possible benefits. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them.

Name (Block Capitals): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____